

Supporting Information

Anodic H₂O₂ Generation in Carbonate-Based Electrolytes— Mechanistic Insight from Scanning Electrochemical Microscopy

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Supporting Information

Anodic H₂O₂ generation in carbonate-based electrolytes – Mechanistic insight from scanning electrochemical microscopy

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1 Experimental section

1.1 Chemicals and materials

Borosilicate double-barrel capillaries (BT-150-10) were purchased from Science Products. The O.D. is 1.5 mm and the wall thickness is 0.25 mm. Au and Pt wires with a diameter of 25 µm were from Goodfellow and the purity of the wires was 99.999 %. The used silver paste E4110-LV was from Epoxy Technology.

The O₂ bubbles evolved during the water oxidation reaction (WOR) can be confined by the porous substrate, which then leads to the aggregation of the small O₂ bubbles under the formation of big ones. Such confinement and aggregation can affect the diffusion of small O₂ bubbles and disturb the O₂ detection at the Pt microelectrode. Therefore, the SECM experiment for the local O₂ detection was conducted over a flat anode. Specifically, 10 mg of ZnGa₂O₄ powder was dispersed in 3 mL isopropanol. After tip sonication, the catalyst suspension was drop-casted on an FTO substrate and heat treated at 500 °C for 2 h in air to obtain the FTO/ZnGa₂O₄ anode for the following SECM

experiments.

The concentration of produced H₂O₂ was quantified based on the spectrophotometric determination of I₃⁻.^[1] Before the quantification step, the aliquot was neutralized by sulfuric acid. The UV absorption spectra were recorded on Cary Series UV-Vis Spectrometer (Agilent Technologies).

1.2 Electrochemical measurements

The anodic H₂O₂ production performance of ZnGa₂O₄ and FTO was conducted in a divided H-cell separated by a Nafion 117 membrane using a Gamry Reference 600 potentiostat/galvanostat. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy at the ZnGa₂O₄/FTO substrate electrode was performed with an AC amplitude of 10 mV_{pp} and in a frequency range between 1 Hz and 100 kHz to determine the uncompensated solution resistance R_u. After iR-drop compensation, the substrate potential was recalculated with respect to the reversible hydrogen electrode RHE according to $E_{RHE} = E_{Ag/AgCl} + 0.21 + 0.059 \times \text{pH}$, and the pH values of the electrolytes were measured using a pH meter (FE28, Mettler Toledo).

1.3 Preparation of Au-Pt double-barrel microelectrodes

Step 1 - Pulling: The capillary was pulled using a homemade “hanging capillary set-up” by applying a current of 17.3 A to the heating coil to melt the capillary. The pulled double-barrel capillary is cut at the end to the desired length and then closed with a flame torch.

Step 2 - Filling: Cut a piece of Pt and a piece of Au wire of approximately 5 mm length. Place the Au and Pt wires separately into the two channels of the capillary, and push them to the tip of the double barrels. Attach the wires to the wall of the capillary by heating with the heating coil.

Step 3 - Sealing: Fix the double-barrel capillary containing the Au and Pt wires again on the “hanging capillary set-up”, and connect the rubber tube to the open end of the capillary and apply vacuum via the pump. Apply 10 A for around 5 min to seal the wires. Check the condition of the wire under the microscope and make sure that half the lengths of both wires in the two barrels are sealed completely inside the glass.

Step 4 - Polishing: Polish the closed end to remove the glass covering from the Au and Pt wire tip. Sandpaper P2000 can be used to polish away the glass until the wires are exposed. Check the distance between the two wire tips.

Step 5 - Connecting: Silver paste was prepared by mixing components A and B with a weight ratio of 10:2. Then the silver paste was filled into the capillary with needles (Ø0.4 × 40 mm) until about half of the capillary was filled. Then silver paste was pushed to the end of the double barrels with a Cu wire. Finally, the Au and the Pt wire were connected to Cu wires after curing at 150 °C for 1 h.

1.4 SECM measurements

All SECM measurements were performed with a homemade SECM setup placed inside a Faraday cage on an active damping table (Newport RS 2000) to prevent vibrational noise. The inner walls

of the Faraday cage were isolated with vacuumed polystyrene panels (Vaku Isotherm) to reduce temperature variations.

Shear-force approach: The approach of the Au tip toward the substrate surface involves two consecutive steps: a pre-approach and a shear-force supported approach. As shown in **Figure S2a**, the pre-approach step was done with the assistance of an optical video microscope to place the Au tip several micrometers away from the anode surface. Subsequently, a fine approach of the Au tip was conducted using the shear-force approach technique. For the shear-force approach, two piezos (Piezomechanik Pickelmann) were mounted to the Au nanoelectrode and connected to a lock-in amplifier (Ametek 7280). The piezo closer to the Au tip is the detection piezo, which was used to measure the phase and the magnitude of the tip oscillation. A second piezo mounted ~2 cm away from the detection piezo serves as the excitation piezo, which induces a tip oscillation based on an AC voltage signal from the oscillator output of the lock-in amplifier. The oscillation magnitude is used as the feedback parameter during the shear-force approach. Frequency scans of the Au tip with piezos and the approach curves can be found in **Figures S2** and **S3**. A detailed description of the shear-force experiments can be found in a previous report.^[2]

Negative feedback approach: O₂ reduction was performed by placing a single 25 μm Pt microelectrode near the FTO-supported ZnGa₂O₄ anode using a negative feedback SECM approach. The working distance for O₂ detection from the FTO/ZnGa₂O₄ anode is approximately 10 μm. For the double-barrel SECM experiments, the Au-Pt double-barrel microelectrode was positioned 10 μm away from the anode surface by means of a negative feedback SECM approach. This approach utilizes the diffusion-limited O₂ reduction in O₂-saturated electrolytes. The Pt tip was polarized at 0.1 V vs. RHE to reduce O₂ in carbonate-based solutions. The diffusion-limited O₂ reduction current at the tip decreased due to the increasing obstruction of the O₂ diffusion by the anode surface as the tip gets closer to the anode. The approach was stopped when the current reached a minimum, determining the final working distance of the Pt tip for subsequent experiments. The distance between the substrate and the double-barrel microelectrode for all the SECM tests is approximately 10 μm.

2 Supplementary Note 1: The equilibrium of carbonic acid substances dissolved in water

There is an equilibrium for dissolved carbonate species in water:

The equilibrium equations of the fractional dissociation of carbonic acid can be expressed as:

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{HCO}_3^-]}{[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]} = 4.45 \times 10^{-7} (25^\circ\text{C})$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{CO}_3^{2-}]}{[\text{HCO}_3^-]} = 4.69 \times 10^{-11} (25^\circ\text{C})$$

Where K₁ and K₂ depend only on the temperature. Accordingly, at a constant temperature, the three carbonate species should be distributed in a fixed proportion determined only by the proton

concentration in the solution.

$$[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3] = C_t \times \alpha_0 \quad \text{Eq. S4}$$

$$[\text{HCO}_3^-] = C_t \times \alpha_1 \quad \text{Eq. S5}$$

$$[\text{CO}_3^{2-}] = C_t \times \alpha_2 \quad \text{Eq. S6}$$

where C_t , α_0 , α_1 , and α_2 represent the total amount of the carbonate species and the distribution ratio of different species.

Combined with equation S1~S3, then α_0 , α_1 , and α_2 can be expressed as a function of the proton concentration as follows:

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{[\text{H}^+] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] \times [\text{H}^+] + K_1 \times [\text{H}^+] + K_1 \times K_2} \quad \text{Eq. S7}$$

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{K_1 \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] \times [\text{H}^+] + K_1 \times [\text{H}^+] + K_1 \times K_2} \quad \text{Eq. S8}$$

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{K_1 \times K_2}{[\text{H}^+] \times [\text{H}^+] + K_1 \times [\text{H}^+] + K_1 \times K_2} \quad \text{Eq. S9}$$

At a constant temperature, the mole ratio of different carbonate species can be calculated according to Eq. 7 ~ 9 in a carbonate-based solution with a known pH value.

3 Supplementary Note 2: The calibration curve for local pH measurements and the Nernst equation

The calibration curve for the local pH was obtained by performing cyclic voltammograms (CVs) at the Au nanoelectrode in a series of calibration solutions with pH values from 5.0 to 12.8 (**Figure S1a**) or at a Au microelectrode with pH values from 2.0 to 12.3 (**Figure S7a**). The potential during the CV at the Au tip was recorded with respect to a Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl reference electrode to visualize the shift of $E(\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3\text{Red})$ caused by the modulation of the local pH value. Au is preferentially oxidized to $\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3$ (Equation S10) in near-neutral/alkaline media and oxidized to Au_2O_3 (Equation S12) in a lower pH range.^[3] The reduction peak potentials of Au- O_x , denoted as $E(\text{Au-}\text{O}_x\text{Red})$, show a clear anodic shift as the solution acidity increases (**Figure S1a** and **S7a**), solely owing to the increasing activity of protons according to the Nernst equation (Eq. S11 and S13). The resulting calibration curve (**Figure S1b** and **S7b**) shows the sensitivity and linearity of the $E(\text{Au-}\text{O}_x\text{Red})$ shift to the solution pH values.

$$E_{\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3/\text{Au}} = E_0 - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \frac{a(\text{Au}) \cdot a(\text{H}_2\text{O})^3}{a(\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3) \cdot a(\text{H}^+)^3} = E_0 - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \frac{a(\text{H}_2\text{O})^3}{a(\text{H}^+)^3} \quad (\text{Eq. S11})$$

$$E_{\text{Au}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}} = E_0 - \frac{RT}{6F} \ln \frac{a(\text{Au})^2 \cdot a(\text{H}_2\text{O})^3}{a(\text{Au}_2\text{O}_3) \cdot a(\text{H}^+)^6} = E_0 - \frac{RT}{6F} \ln \frac{a(\text{H}_2\text{O})^3}{a(\text{H}^+)^6} \quad (\text{Eq. S13})$$

Table S1 Anodic H₂O₂ generation in HCO₃⁻-based solutions

Catalyst	Electrolyte	^a Potential (V versus RHE)	FE (%)	Maximum H ₂ O ₂ generation rate	Ref
BiVO₄	1 M NaHCO ₃	3.1	70	5.77 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[4]
BiVO₄:6%Gd	2 M KHCO ₃	3.1	78	10.6 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[5]
CaSnO₃	2 M KHCO ₃	3.2	76	4.6 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[6]
ZnO	2 M KHCO ₃	2.6	81	^b 4.15 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[7]
Sb₂O₃	2 M KHCO ₃	3.08	22	0.26 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[8]
Bi₂WO₆:5%Mo	2 M KHCO ₃	3.2	79	5 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[9]
BDD	2 M KHCO ₃	2.48	20.1	-	[10]
CuWO₄:Sn	2 M KHCO ₃	2.5	72	11.6 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[11]
ZnGa₂O₄	2 M KHCO ₃	2.3	82	22.5 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[12]

^aNB: The potential corresponding to the highest FE. ^bNB: H₂O₂ production rate is calculated based on the values of $j_{H_2O_2}$ reported.

Table S2 Anodic H₂O₂ generation in CO₃²⁻-based solutions

Catalyst	Electrolyte	^a Potential (V versus RHE)	FE (%)	Maximum H ₂ O ₂ generation rate/H ₂ O ₂ partial current	Ref
BDD	2 M K ₂ CO ₃	3.1	41.2	-	[10]
BDD	2 M K ₂ CO ₃ /KHCO ₃ (salt ratios 1:1)	2.85	87	76.4 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[13]
CFP- 60%PTFE	1 M Na ₂ CO ₃	2.4	66	23.4 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[14]
ZnGa₂O₄	2 M K ₂ CO ₃	2.9	77	69 μmol cm ⁻² min ⁻¹	[12]
FTO	1 M NaHCO ₃	3.0	34	5.6 mA cm ⁻²	[15]

FTO	1 M Na ₂ CO ₃	3.2	56	50 mA cm ⁻²	[15]
FTO	5 M K ₂ CO ₃	3.46	87	522 mA cm ⁻²	[15]
LaAlO₃	2 M K ₂ CO ₃	3.5	23	-	[16]
LaAlO₃	4 M K ₂ CO ₃ /KHCO ₃ (pH=11)	3.34	87	-	[16]

^aNB: The potential corresponding to the highest FE. ^bNB: The H₂O₂ production rate is calculated based on the values of $j_{H_2O_2}$ reported.

Table S3 Local pH shift in carbonate-based electrolytes

Electrolyte	E_{sub}/mV vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl	I_{sub}/mA	E(Au-O_xRed)/mV vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl	Local pH change
2.0 M KHCO₃	1200 ~ 2700	0 ~ 1.44	345 ~ 567	8.3 ~ 5.0
1.0 M KHCO₃	1200 ~ 2700	0 ~ 1.05	323 ~ 612	8.6 ~ 4.3
0.5 M KHCO₃	1200 ~ 2700	0 ~ 0.75	331 ~ 642	8.3 ~ 3.8
0.2 M KHCO₃	1200 ~ 2700	0 ~ 0.43	325 ~ 700	8.6 ~ 3.1
2 M KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ mixed solution with a pH of 10.3	1312 ~ 2712	0 ~ 2.05	226 ~ 311	10.2 ~ 8.9
2 M K₂CO₃	1436 ~ 2736	0 ~ 0.98	112 ~ 227	12.3 ~ 10.5

3 Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. (a) CVs at the Au nanoelectrode (diameter ~ 700 nm) recorded in a series of calibration solutions with different pH values. (b) Linear fits of the relationship between $E(\text{Au}(\text{OH})_{3\text{Red}})$ and the solution pH values.

Figure S2. (a) Optical microscopy image of the pre-approached Au tip above the carbon paper-supported ZnGa_2O_4 (CP/ ZnGa_2O_4) anode. (b) Frequency scans of the Au tip oscillation magnitude recorded in air and while being immersed in the bulk electrolyte. (c) Shear-force approach curve of the Au tip at a tip resonant oscillation frequency of 361 kHz during the approach towards the catalyst surface.

Figure S3. (a) Frequency scans of the Au tip magnitude recorded in air and during immersion in the bulk electrolyte. (b) Shear-force approach curve of the Au tip at a resonant oscillation frequency of 470 kHz during the approach towards the catalyst surface.

Figure S4. CVs at the Au tip in (a) 2.0 M KHCO₃ electrolytes containing different concentrations of H₂O₂ and in (c) 2.0 M K₂CO₃ electrolytes containing different concentrations of H₂O₂. The reduction peak potential of Au(OH)₃ was plotted against the H₂O₂ concentration (b) in 2.0 M KHCO₃ and (d) in 2.0 M K₂CO₃. The reduction peak potentials were averaged over three independent measurements.

Figure S5. (a) Schematic illustration of the fabrication of the double barrel Au-Pt microelectrode. Optical microscopy images of (b) the double-barrel capillary loaded with 25 μm Au and Pt wires in

separate channels, (c) with the Au and Pt wires sealed in the glass, (d) after polishing the tips, and (e) the cross-section of the tip surface.

Figure S6. (a) pH-dependent CVs at the Au tip of the double-barrel microelectrode in a series of calibration solutions with pH values ranging from 2.0 to 12.3. (b) Calibration curve derived from the reduction peak potentials of Au-O_x as a function of the solution pH values. The reduction peak potentials were averaged over three measurements. The calibration curve in **Figure S6b** shows a super-Nernstian correlation with a slope of 66.5 mV pH⁻¹.

Figure S7. (a) CVs at the Pt tip of the double-barrel microelectrode in 2.0 M KHCO₃ solution with different concentrations of H₂O₂. (b) The calibration curve for H₂O₂ detection at the Pt tip in 2.0 M KHCO₃ solution. The CVs in **Figure S7a** demonstrate, that H₂O₂ can be oxidized or reduced at the Pt tip, and a linear correlation was observed by plotting the tip current at 520 mV vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl against H₂O₂ concentration (**Figure 7b**).

Figure S8. CVs at the Au tip positioned in close proximity to the FTO substrate when a series of substrate potentials was applied in 2.0 M KHCO_3 .

Figure S9. (a) Chronoamperometry test of the water oxidation current (substrate current, i_{sub}) and the detection current of H_2O_2 ($i_{\text{tip-H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ oxidation}}$) recorded by Pt tip in 2.0 M KHCO_3 . It reveals that H_2O_2 starts to be detected when E_{sub} reaches 2100 mV vs. RHE, and the tip current keeps coincides with the increase in i_{sub} in the evaluated range of E_{sub} .

Figure S10. Time trace of the substrate current and the O₂ reduction current recorded at the Pt tip. The Pt tip was polarized at -400 mV vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl in 2.0 M KHCO₃ solution. A detectable O₂ reduction reaction current at the Pt tip was observed when E_{sub} reaches 2000 mV vs. RHE, which is more negative than the detection threshold of H₂O₂ oxidation. This can be rationalized considering that the thermodynamic potential of OER is less positive compared to that of anodic H₂O₂ formation.

Figure S11. Investigation of the local pH shift in vicinity of an FTO surface in 1.0, 0.5, 0.2 M bicarbonate solution. CVs recorded at the Au tip close to the FTO substrate in (a) 1.0 M KHCO_3 , (b) 0.5 M KHCO_3 , and (c) 0.2 M KHCO_3 , when a series of substrate potentials was applied to FTO electrode. The extracted values of i_{sub} , $E(\text{Au-O}_{\text{xRed}})$, and the calculated pH values as a function of E_{sub} are shown in (d) 1.0 M KHCO_3 , (e) 0.5 M KHCO_3 , and (f) 0.2 M KHCO_3 .

Voltammograms at the Au tip were recorded while increasing the WOR overpotential applied to E_{sub} . As expected, for all electrolyte conditions, a similar anodic shift of the reduction peak position of Au-O_x was evidenced in **Figure S11 a ~ c**. However, it is found that $E(\text{Au-O}_{\text{xRed}})$ demonstrates different degrees of anodic shift in different scenarios. Specifically, as shown in **Figure S11 d ~ f**, the anodic shift of $E(\text{Au-O}_{\text{xRed}})$ was observed to be 612 mV in 1.0 M KHCO_3 , 642 mV in 0.5 M KHCO_3 , and 700 mV vs. RHE in 0.2 M KHCO_3 when E_{sub} was stepped from 1200 to 2700 mV vs. RHE, while the local pH decreased from 8.4 to 3.4 in 1.0 M KHCO_3 , from 8.3 to 3.0 in 0.5 M KHCO_3 , and from 8.6 to 2.1 in 0.2 M KHCO_3 . Interestingly, the water oxidation current (i_{sub}) increased from 0 to 1.05 mA in 1.0 M KHCO_3 , to 0.75 mA in 0.5 M KHCO_3 , to 0.43 mA in 0.2 M KHCO_3 , respectively. A summary of the E_{sub} , i_{sub} , i_{tip} , and local pH change can be found in **Table S3**.

Figure S12. Chronoamperometry measurement and the corresponding WOR current (substrate current, i_{sub}) and the detection current for H_2O_2 ($i_{\text{tip-H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ oxidation}}$) recorded at the positioned Pt tip in (a) 1.0 M KHCO_3 , (b) 0.5 M KHCO_3 , (c) 0.2 M KHCO_3 . The extracted values of i_{sub} and $i_{\text{tip-H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ oxidation}}$ are plotted as a function of the applied substrate potentials in (d) 1.0 M KHCO_3 , (e) 0.5 M KHCO_3 , (f) 0.2 M KHCO_3 .

Figure S13. Local pH shift in the vicinity of an FTO surface in 2.0 M KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ (pH 10.3) and 2.0 M K₂CO₃ (pH 12.3). CVs recorded at the Au tip close to the FTO substrate in (a) 2.0 M KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ (pH 10.3), (c) 2.0 M K₂CO₃ (pH 12.3). The extracted values of i_{sub} , $E(\text{Au-O}_{\text{sRed}})$, and the calculated pH values as a function of E_{sub} in (b) 2.0 M KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ (pH 10.3), (d) 2.0 M K₂CO₃ (pH 12.3). The local pH decreased from 10.3 to 8.9 as E_{sub} increased from 1310 to 2712 mV in a mixed carbonate solution with a pH of 10.3, and decreased from 12.3 to 10.5 as E_{sub} increased from 1436 to 2736 mV in 2.0 M K₂CO₃, respectively.

Figure S14. Chronoamperometry test of the water oxidation current (substrate current, i_{sub}) and the detection current of H₂O₂ ($i_{\text{tip-H}_2\text{O}_2}$ oxidation) recorded by Pt tip in (a) 2.0 M KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ (pH 10.3),

(c) 2.0 M K₂CO₃ (pH 12.3). The extracted values of i_{sub} and $i_{\text{tip-H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ oxidation}}$ as function of substrate potentials in (b) 2.0 M KHCO₃/K₂CO₃ (pH 10.3), (d) 2.0 M K₂CO₃ (pH 12.3).

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